

wide and furrows 30 cm wide were prepared. The field was irrigated to capacity. Thirty-day-old seedlings of 8 rice cultivars (see table) were transplanted on the sides of the ridges at 30- × 10-cm spacing with 2-3 seedlings/hill, in a randomized block design with 6 replications.

A basal application of 50 kg N/ha, 13 kg P/ha, and 30 kg K/ha was broadcast before ridges and furrows were prepared. Nitrogen at 25 kg/ha was applied in a band 5 cm away from planted rows at 20 and 45 days after transplanting. The crop was hand-weeded twice during

Performance of rice cultivars transplanted under nonpuddled conditions. Mandya, India, 1980 kharif (wet season).

Cultivar	Duration (days)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Rasi	125	4.4
IR20	150	3.7
Mangala	110	3.6
IRAT 2	150	3.5
Jaya	160	3.2
IRAT 10	144	3.2
Lagore	144	2.8
IRAT 13	116	2.0
CD (0.05)		0.11
CV (%)		29

the early stages of crop growth. A fair distribution of rains during the season made protective irrigation unnecessary.

Results indicated that, of the eight rices tested, Rasi recorded the significantly highest yield, followed by IR20 and Mangala (see table). These rices had early and good stand establishment, satisfactory canopy cover with high panicle number, and low spikelet sterility. The rice yields obtained were very competitive with those of ragi grown under similar conditions. □

Foliar spraying *Eichhornia* inoculum and incorporation of *Eichhornia* and *Ipomoea* green leaves as supplemental nitrogen sources

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The aquatic weeds *Eichhornia crassipes* and *Ipomoea carnea*, unlike conventional green leaf manures, are abundant. An experiment was conducted in a randomized block design, replicated four times, on the College Farm, Rajendranagar, in the 1977 wet season to determine the effect of *Eichhornia* inoculum spraying and *Eichhornia* and *Ipomoea* green leaf incorporation in the nitrogen economy of rice. One hundred milliliters of *Eichhornia* spray solution with a count of 23.1 × 10⁹/ml was diluted 10 times and sprayed in each 13.5-m² plot. In treatments with 2% urea spray, 1,000 ml of 2% urea solution was sprayed in each plot.

Grain yield was highest (4.1 t/ha) in the treatment with 100 kg N/ha (see table). It was on par with the yields in treatments that received 60 kg N/ha + *Eichhornia* leaves; 60 kg N/ha + *Ipomoea* leaves, and with 60 kg N/ha + 2% urea

Effect of *Eichhornia* inoculum spray and leaf incorporation of *Eichhornia* and *Ipomoea* with nitrogen application on rice yields. Rajendranagar, Hyderabad, India.

Treatment	Grain		Straw	
	Yield (t/ha)	Increase (%) over yield with 60 kg N/ha	Yield (t/ha)	Increase (%) over yield with 60 kg N/ha
100 kg N/ha	4.1	24	4.7	30
60 kg N/ha + <i>Ipomoea</i> leaf incorporation at 10 t/ha	3.9	18	4.2	17
60 kg N/ha + <i>Eichhornia</i> leaf incorporation at 10 t/ha	3.8	15	4.2	17
60 kg N/ha + 2% urea solution spray	3.8	15	3.8	6
60 kg N/ha + <i>Eichhornia</i> inoculum spray	3.7	12	3.5	97
60 kg N/ha + 2% urea spray + <i>Eichhornia</i> inoculum spray	3.5	6	3.9	8
60 kg N/ha	3.3	—	3.6	—
C.D. at 5%	0.4	—	0.4	—

spray. Yield differences between the treatment with 60 kg N/ha + 2% urea solution spray and that with 60 kg N/ha + *Eichhornia* inoculum spray were insignificant. That indicates a spraying of *Eichhornia* inoculum is as effective as 3 sprayings of 2% urea. *E. crassipes* and *I.*

carnea weeds, when used as green manure at 10 t/ha, provide supplementary 40 kg N/ha and increase rice grain yield. They do not proliferate in the field during succeeding seasons, however, if the leaves are properly incorporated before rice is planted. □

Fertilizer usage and productivity of aus, aman, and boro rice

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A study of 225 randomly selected farmers was conducted in Haringhata block, West Bengal, India, to determine the relationship between levels of fertilizer usage and rice yields during different seasons. Data for the preceding year were collected from January to March

1981.

Multiple regression analysis revealed that NPK levels used explained 73% of the variation in boro (dry season-winter rice) yields, 40% variation in aus (September, pre wet-season) yields, and 7% variation in aman (wet season) yields.